

Fecha: 23-01-12 [17:51:24 CET]
De: The Lancet Team <em@editorialmanager.com>
Para: Manuel Graña <manuel.grana@ehu.eus>
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Your submission entitled "Recovering trust in the vaccines" has been received by The Lancet Journal Office.

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